

BIO-SHARE IN LIQUID FUELS ACHIEVED THROUGH BIOMASS INTEGRATION IN REFINERY

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Introduction

During the last two centuries, CO₂ accumulation has been observed in the atmosphere. CO₂ is a greenhouse gas which contributes to global warming. Therefore, there is an increased interest in reducing CO₂ emissions caused by the burning of fossil fuels.

One of the means how to eliminate this CO₂ cumulation is replacement of fossil fuels by biofuels. These are made for example from energy-rich plants such as corn, or richly available plants such as trees. Of course, burning a tree creates CO₂ as well but these trees are replaced by new ones that consume the created CO₂ hence, closing the cycle [1].

Currently, a lot of bio-share commanded by EU is achieved through growing energy dedicated plants for FAME production which is ultimately mixed with fossil fuel. But this is economically demanding, causes deforestation and competes with food increasing its price.

Solution: producing biofuel from biomass residue.

Experimental

We have analyze dozens of articles dealing with the integration of biomass residue into the refinery, considering economical, logistical and technical aspect of the problem. We plan to make a model impact on the refinery in these fields. Results of this work will be used for the creation of a bachelor project.

Objectives:

1. Word document overviewing all important aspects.
2. Excel tables listing all articles with the most important information sorted out in columns.
3. Excel economic model of proposed investment.
4. Bachelor work including Word document for bachelor work as well as an excel evaluation model.

Results and Discussion

To date, analysis has led to the key findings as follows:

1. Pyrolysis or hydrothermal liquefaction of biomass is the most considered process for biomass to liquid conversion.
2. Liquifying biomass in the place of origin and subsequent transport seems to be economically more advantageous than transporting biomass [2].
3. Pyrolysis requires cheaper equipment compared to hydrothermal liquefaction and is considered as more promising [3].
4. There is a synergy when co-processing of VGO + bio-oil in FCC unit [4]. VGO can serve as a hydrogen donor for bio-oil for which FCC catalyst is quite suitable.

5. Feeds have similar distillation curves.
6. 5-10% share of bio-oil in VGO can be processed without extensive impact of product yields.
7. Feasibility of bio-oil co-processing was already confirmed in the demonstration scale FCC unit in Brazil [5,6].

Up till now, it seems that fast pyrolysis of biomass in the place of origin and subsequent transport of bio-oil to the refinery followed by the addition of small amount (5-10%) of bio-oil to VGO stream intended for FCC is the most viable option

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